

AI: Is It a Protector From Unfairness or Just a Blanketed Bias Machine?

Elif Ezerel¹

*Department of Psychology
Faculty of Social Sciences
and Humanities
Koç University
Istanbul, Türkiye
ezerel20@ku.edu.tr*

Abstract— As artificial intelligence (AI) becomes integrated into an increasing number of aspects of our lives, it is clear that AI has the power to revolutionize decision-making processes. This study focuses on how skewed data sets and algorithms could promote ableism and prejudice against disabled applicants. Additionally, it discusses the use of facial recognition technology in hiring procedures, the lack of oversight, and the need to consider the variety of disabilities. Finally, the conclusion addresses the limitations of AI in representing the diversity and fluidity of human identity and experiences.

Keywords— *Artificial intelligence, Algorithmic bias, Ableism, Technoableism, Disability discrimination, Bias in AI, Ethical AI*

Artificial intelligence (AI) has the ability to completely transform decision-making processes, and this is evident in a time when AI is being incorporated into more and more facets of our lives. AI advocates claim that by reducing or even eliminating human biases, their system may produce more equal and objective results [1]. This optimistic perspective, however, ignores a crucial problem; the ingrained biases in the algorithms themselves. These prejudices frequently support discrimination and inequality, especially towards people with disabilities. The hiring process is one instance where this issue is most noticeable. Even though AI is supposed to be unbiased, the data and training algorithms that are employed might unintentionally reinforce preexisting biases, which can be detrimental to job applicants with disabilities. This paper focuses on how these biased data sets, and algorithms, may enable ableism and discriminate against disabled people during recruitment processes.

Ableism is the explicit or implicit preference for non-disabled bodies and brains, as well as the negative attitudes that follow towards disability and individuals with disabilities. Our expectations and views are shaped by ableism. These biases against disability and handicapped individuals are evident in the physical environment as well as in the institutional and societal norms that influence day-to-day existence [2].

The behaviours and circumstances that marginalise or prevent the contributions of disabled people, remove them from communal life, and reject first-hand accounts of their experiences are all rooted in ableism. One such example is technoableism. The term "technoableism" refers to a discourse on disability that both emphasises the use of technology to empower disabled people while promoting ableist stereotypes about who is deserving and what kinds of bodies and minds are desirable. Artificial Intelligence and machine learning are the most recent wave of technological remedies to the perceived issues faced by individuals with disabilities. AIs that are being developed now have several instances of ableism [2].

Many definitions of artificial intelligence base their meaning on analogies with human thinking. According to these definitions, AI is sophisticated technology intended to mimic human intellect. AI is also capable of carrying out activities that previously needed human involvement. In reality, AI is just software with the ability to learn, decide, complete tasks, and solve problems [3]. Moreover, as it has been said to be almost 'bias free', most companies are starting to use it in their recruitment programs [4]. The increasing prevalence of automated employment solutions can be attributed to advancements in machine learning and data analytics. By incorporating AI into the recruiting process—from locating applicants and evaluating applications to automating interviews—employers want to maximise hiring efficiency. Hiring AIs compare applicants to previous workers or look for personality factors linked to high performance to find the ones who are most likely to "fit" or flourish in the job. Endorsers assert that their algorithms enable firms to increase recruiting diversity since they are not only more effective than human recruiters but also less biased. Despite the excitement surrounding AI's ability to boost diversity in hiring, many vendors rely on ambiguously defined notions of bias and inadequately represented data, which make it difficult to understand how bias might be reflected in AI and potentially worsened [5].

AI uses a set of data, also known as its training data, to teach the AI how to learn, decide and solve problems. Algorithms, which are essentially a collection of instructions that can be followed step-by-step to arrive at a certain output, are necessary for AI to function. Algorithms, like all technology, should be viewed as manifestations of power and control and as a system rather than as discrete objects. Even while algorithms are frequently promoted as a means of measuring fairness and making decision-making more objective, there are many different interpretations of what constitutes "fairness," many of which are mutually exclusive or entail substantial trade-offs [6].

AI programmes may have different effects when trained on nonrepresentative datasets, even in cases where material specifically referencing protected classes is not included. It is true that datasets may exaggerate the associations between belonging to a group and unfavourable outcomes. Vulnerable groups are more likely to have their mistakes observed, documented, and utilised as training data for algorithms since they are frequently the targets of excessive scrutiny. For instance, because information on handicapped persons is disproportionately obtained in settings related to addiction, homelessness, and violence, language processing AI links the mention of disability to those conditions. In addition, algorithms may not be able to identify patterns in datasets that underrepresent particular groups; instead, they may concentrate on the majority in order to prevent overfitting. However, the methods of issue framing, proxy selection, and data labeling are also responsible for algorithmic bias, in addition to unrepresentative datasets and erroneous input-output linkages. Making vague requirements, like "fit" and "employability," comprehensible to AI is a process shaped by societal conventions and attitudes rather than being impartial. For instance, if AI systems that simulate "employability" in terms of good posture, fluent communication, and consistent eye contact were flawless, they would discriminate against a large number of candidates with disabilities. When presented with scant or heterogeneous data, data scientists must also make arbitrary judgements about the selection of proxy variables or the aggregation of attributes. This might lead to introduction of biases, loss of accuracy and poor policy and decision-making. [5]

It has been stated that the recruitment system will undoubtedly be fair if it is unaware of a person's handicap status. Employers may believe that by outsourcing the evaluation to an ostensibly "neutral" AI and doing away with traditional human prejudice, they are assisting candidates with disabilities. That being said, this ignores the likelihood that white, able-bodied men invented the instruments in the first place [7]. The issue lies in the fact that the impairment frequently affects other data points that are given in the model. A blind person will need more time to browse the page before they can respond to the inquiry if the test programme is poorly constructed [8].

If that time isn't taken into account when evaluating them, then everyone with a comparable impairment using the same instrument will be systematically disadvantaged. This is a result of norm learning in machine learning systems. They don't give outliers any particular treatment; instead, they optimise for norms. However, those with impairments don't always fit the mould [8].

Another example is recruitment videos. Among these businesses offering video interviews is HireVue, which creates technologies utilised by almost one hundred well-known corporations, like Unilever, JP Morgan, and Shell. By rating candidates based on a variety of criteria, the programme employs artificial intelligence (AI) to assist in the analysis of job video interviews and identify the most qualified applicant [9]. As a consequence, psychological judgements about a person's likelihood of succeeding in a position are drawn from their facial data. A person with a facial difference is likely to score lower when facial recognition technology is employed during the interview process [10]. This will result in more discrimination against disabled people. There are people with facial disfigurement due to their diseases, people who had strokes cannot often control one side of their faces or blind people may not even look at the camera during their interviews. AI may be fair in its judgement, however literature and field results show that the dataset that AI is trained upon is biased.

Ableism is a topic people claim to know about but in reality we haven't even scratched the surface. This topic was interesting for me on a personal note because I am also disabled and use a wheelchair. I have experienced being the other in our society firsthand, especially in recruitment. However, this is about to be even more exacerbated by the use of AI. It's a valiant effort to minimize and in the future hopefully eliminate all the bias disabled people experience in recruitment with the use of AI tools. This doesn't seem possible at the moment. However, people should also realise the fault isn't only in the process but also in the datasets that companies train their AI tools on. We cannot just say we have done our due duty of making AI fair and leave a developing part of technology alone to develop with these preexisting biases. Incorporating disability perspectives into AI discussions reveals AI's limitations in capturing the fluidity and complexity of human identity and experiences. With this discussion, hopefully even more companies will be inspired to discuss these topics and show the preexisting and possible problems.

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